

EDUCATION IN PROGRESS "DEVELOPMENT OF CREATIVE PROBLEMS H " METHOD

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Abstract: In this article in the organization of technological education processes and improvement of the management system When using the "Creative problem development" method in the course of the lesson, the situational approach is used to determine the effectiveness of education and training processes according to specific situations, in training sessions based on the activity of the problem approach, in the students' finding solutions to problematic issues, in various problematic situations. ability to accurately solve tasks in situations, the level of knowledge of students, the effectiveness of the educational process, and the process of developing independent thinking skills of students were observed.

The peculiarity of the situational approach is that it is recommended to use the "Development of creative issues" method in the course of the lesson to identify important problems based on the analysis of situations in the course of the lesson and to predetermine the effectiveness of the results to be achieved in different situations. ...

Keywords: Technological education, technological process, creative problem, pedagogical technology, heuristic education, cognitive method, creative problem, work culture, interactive method.

ОБУЧЕНИЕ В ПРОЦЕССЕ «РАЗРАБОТКА ТВОРЧЕСКИХ ЗАДАЧ Ч» МЕТОД

Аннотация: В данной статье в организации технологических процессов обучения и совершенствовании системы управления. При использовании метода «Творческая разработка задачи» в ходе урока используется ситуационный подход для определения эффективности учебно-воспитательных процессов по конкретным ситуациям, на учебных занятиях, основанных на деятельности проблемного подхода, в поиске студентами решений проблемных вопросов, в различных проблемных ситуациях. наблюдались способность точно решать задачи в ситуациях, уровень знаний студентов, эффективность учебного процесса, процесс развития навыков самостоятельного мышления студентов.

Особенность ситуационного подхода заключается в том, что метод «Разработка творческих задач» рекомендуется использовать в ходе урока для выявления важных проблем на основе анализа ситуаций в ходе урока и предопределения эффективности проводимой работы. результаты, которых необходимо достичь в различных ситуациях. ...

Ключевые слова: технологическое образование, технологический процесс, творческая задача, педагогическая технология, эвристическое образование, когнитивный метод, творческая задача, культура труда, интерактивный метод.

INTRODUCTION

The content of teaching, the organizational form of the lesson process, the use of technical and technological tools, and the methods of teaching in order to implement the educational, educational, developmental, practical and creative tasks in the organization of technological

education processes and the improvement of the teacher's management activities. It is of particular importance. All the above-mentioned elements are the basis for increasing the quality and efficiency of the educational process. The main condition for the transition to each stage of development is not only the regular increase of labor productivity and the creation of abundance of material goods, but also the education of high moral qualities in the young generation and the education process. It is required to raise to the heights. First of all, it is formed in the educational processes that are carried out for the benefit of the society of technology, the students are educated to take care of the equipment in the workshop, to use raw materials sparingly. Work culture in educational workshops, organization of workplace and proper planning of educational and work activities, use of various devices along with hand tools in technology science and vocational education classes are of great importance. Because they not only improve the quality of students' work, but also increase labor productivity. The teacher's personal example during demonstration of labor and craft methods is considered a powerful educational tool for students.

The goals and tasks of labor and vocational education are implemented in the process of practical training in technology lessons. So, practical training is an educational work that is carried out under the guidance of a technology teacher for the purpose of active, conscious and solid mastering of the educational material by students, and includes both team and individual types of work. It is necessary to understand the organization of activities.

Nowadays, it is necessary to organize the educational process in different ways in order to form students as well-rounded individuals. Because it allows the student to search for answers to the questions he is interested in through the Internet. However, the student understands the meaning of this activity only if he acquires knowledge, skills and abilities through academic subjects.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODOLOGY

The number of innovative technologies and interactive methods in education has increased greatly. The method of "Development of creative issues" that we recommend has its own characteristics.

Its main object of analysis is creative thinking systems. Concepts such as creative approach and creative thinking are included in the method of "Development of creative issues". The method of "Development of creative issues" is knowledge in the field of the theory of solving creative issues and the mechanisms of technical development.

The purpose of using this method is to use the technology of developing the student's creativity, i.e. creative thinking. It should be noted that many methods of general didactic nature are used in the process of technology science. However, such methods as practical demonstration of work methods, exercises related to their implementation, working with technical references and technological documents, and performance of educational production tasks are methods specific to the "Science of Technology". It is possible to organize training using many types of pedagogical technology in technology classes. Pedagogical technology is aimed at the comprehensive development of the child's curiosity.

Pedagogical scientist A. Kushner believes that the methodology is a way of popularizing best practice or inventing a new way of imparting knowledge, and the result cannot always be guaranteed.

And technology is a process that gives a predetermined result, no matter what the circumstances [1].

The science of technology is connected with the tools, methods and forms of pedagogical technology. Pedagogical technology in the course of the lesson ensures the training of personnel at the level of the requirements of the state educational standards in the conditions of mass education. Our ultimate goal is to deliver independent-minded, creative, inquisitive and talented young people for the future.

The "Development of creative issues" method in improving the mechanisms of organization and management of technological education processes in general secondary schools is one of the urgent problems in the implementation of the pedagogical process based on heuristic education.

Heuristic education relies on the level of knowledge of students and three integrative skills in the development of the educational process of the educational institution. These are types of creative, cognitive and creative process (*a process formed during organizational activity*).

By heuristic education, we understand the complex possibilities of students to perform activities and actions aimed at creating an object, detail or product.

In order to form complex opportunities, it is necessary to have the potential of research in students.

The capacity for innovation is understood as the process of deep understanding of the ability of individuals to generate unique ideas and make innovative decisions. The main demand for education today is related to the development of a creative person who can go beyond certain boundaries, make non-standard decisions, and create innovative products.

When describing creativity, psychologists refer to the problem of ability and often consider creativity as a general creative ability, a process of changing knowledge [2]. They are also said to be associated with imaginative development and hypothesis generation.

According to Abraham Maslow, the influential American psychologist, "The term creativity is innate and universal, and it is a creative direction that many people lose under the influence of the external environment."

According to the American psychologist EP Torrens, creativity - non-standard, creative thinking ability of an individual, "sensitivity to the mutual opposition of knowledge and practical actions in finding a solution to a problem, the ability to search and find solutions to problems based on the promotion of new hypotheses, to identify, verify and change hypotheses, to formulate decision results" - he explains.

The creative process includes several stages that require different intellectual properties. These thoughts G. Wallace, one of the artists, in 1926 defined four stages of the creative process, which have since been considered classic and appear in one form or another in all modern classifications. They are as follows:

1. Preparation. Assessment of the problem, initial attempts to find a solution. Here, logical thinking is more in demand and allows you to identify gaps in existing knowledge.

2. Incubation. When a person is engaged in other issues and does not make direct attempts to solve the problem, but continues to search for its solution at the subconscious level, it is necessary to temporarily postpone the determination of the solution to this problem.

3. Lighting up. insight - The solution to the problem appears suddenly, no matter how much, and often occurs when a person is not thinking about this problem. At this stage, as in the previous stage, a person's ability to imagine plays a key role in solving the problem, rather than creative thinking.

4. Assessment - like preparation, is mainly based on traditional, logical thinking [3].

It is known that in the implementation of the following types of educational activities, the following qualities of a person are manifested as a creative process:

1. Creative (creativity) qualities are inspiration, fantasy, sharpness of mind, sensitivity to contradictions, clarity of thoughts and feelings, having one's own opinion.
2. Cognitive qualities are the ability to feel the world around, to ask questions, to search for the cause of events, to express whether one understands the essence of the question or not.
3. Creative activity (methodological organizational activity) qualities include the ability to determine the purpose of educational activity and explain them, the ability to set a goal for oneself, reflexive thinking skills.

In improving the organization and management of technological educational processes, the teacher's knowledge of the system of ideas, solving problems in specific situations, and taking into account the results of their application in a voluntary pedagogical system will help in advance. In education and training processes, it is necessary to analyze the effectiveness of the results achieved in different situations, and the situational approach in the analytical process is of special importance [4].

Therefore, it is one of the most effective ways to organize technological education processes and to coordinate the activities of students according to the situations that are formed in the improvement of the teacher's management activities. holds [5].

Therefore, the optimal method of management depending on the internal and external situation of the managed object in specific conditions is the situational approach [6].

In our opinion, the specific aspects of the situational approach can be seen in the following directions:

- to identify important problems based on the analysis of the situations of the educational process;
- predetermining the effectiveness of the results to be achieved according to different situations.

It is important to take into account the following aspects in the implementation of the situational approach technology in the organization of technological educational processes according to specific situations, in ensuring student knowledge and the effectiveness of the educational process:

- study, analysis and objective evaluation of the situations arising in the education and training processes;
- predetermining achievable results according to various pedagogical situations that arise chronically;
- it is of particular importance to choose the means of ensuring student activity based on pre-imagining the factors affecting the educational and educational processes and the situations that may arise.

RESULTS

It is known that the importance of organization and management of technological education processes is reflected in its effectiveness.

Effectiveness is expressed in the activity of students in the course of the lesson and in various developments. Therefore, regardless of the scope and dynamics of the achieved results, it is important to plan the work and the methods to be implemented in advance, and implement the management technology for the results.

The concept of management by results, as a development system, represents a set of actions aimed at developing previously achieved results on the basis of coordinating the activities of students in education and training processes and ensuring their activity. [7-11] . In the implementation of management technology, the mechanisms of conveying the essence of the subject to the students to each student, the methods used, the self-management of students and the introduction of an analytical approach to their activities are envisaged. necessary.

Cognitive (cognitive) qualities imply focusing on the creation of innovative education that forms creative abilities while improving the mechanisms of organization and management of technological education processes in general secondary schools.

Creative (creativity) qualities provide the conditions for creating a product of creativity by the student in the process of general secondary education. These are:

- emotional-image qualities: inspiration, emotional uplift in creative situations, imagery, imagination, fantasy, dreaminess, romanticism, sense of novelty, prediction of search;
- preparing to come up with an inventive initiative;
- the ability to generalize thoughts;
- that acquisition of diversity of ideas is compatible with norms of etiquette in school, family, social environment;
- the ability to conduct a conversation with the studied object, the ability to choose learning methods, the ability to determine the structure and content, the ability to determine the relationship between the objects of the approach.

The qualities of creative activity (methodological organizational activity) are manifested in knowledge and creativity in the process of organizing student education:

- the student's knowledge of the characteristics of his individual activity;
- to be able to understand and explain one's purpose through study subjects;
- the existence of appropriate programs, content, completion of the work started, commitment to the goal, striving for the goal, and remaining committed to achieving the goal;
- to be able to set an educational goal in a given field, to make a plan for success, to implement the set plan based on one's individual abilities, to achieve and understand one's own results, to compare one's results with the results of classmates;
- formation of rules of operation, formation of the system of its laws;
- self-organization skills: activity planning, programming, correction (editing) of activity stages and methods, orderliness of activity, keeping alternative thoughts in the mind at the same time;
- self-monitoring, analysis and evaluation;
- being able to interact with other subjects of education and the environment, being able to stick to one's idea, protection, determination;
- the ability to organize creativity in others, to study and process the ideas of other students, to organize a brainstorming session, to participate in it, to compare ideas, to argue and debate.

DISCUSSION

When discussing new aspects of solving educational and professional tasks, their thinking will be strengthened, and at the same time, new skills and competencies will be formed in students. It allows to gather experience of creative solution of various educational and professional tasks. It should be noted that the large number of students in the classes often feel passive in the process of mastering the learning material, so the use of teaching methods that

encourage students to be active in independent and creative activities is today's trend. we can see that it is manifested as an urgent necessity and need .

So, if we take into account that when using the "Development of creative issues" method in the course of the lesson, the situational approach is intended to determine the effectiveness of the educational and educational processes according to specific situations, and in the training sessions conducted on the basis of the activity of the problem approach, in determining students' solutions to problematic issues, the level of students' knowledge, the effectiveness of the educational process, and the process of forming students' independent thinking skills increase to a higher level.

It can be concluded that the specific aspects of the situational approach, in the organization of technological education processes It is important to use the "Creative problem development" method, to identify problems based on the analysis of situations in the course of the lesson, and to predetermine the effectiveness of the results to be achieved in different situations.

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